

Crystal structure of iron(III) complex with pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid

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Complex of Fe^{III} with pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid has been synthesized. The ligand acts as tridentate coordinating through the heterocyclic ring nitrogen and two carboxyl oxygens. A single crystal X-ray analysis on the complex reveals the structure as distorted octahedral, Fe sitting at the center and surrounded by the two tridentate ligands.

The reactions of Fe^{III} and Fe^{II} with pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acids (H₂L) have been extensively studied and their crystal structures are reported¹⁻⁴ in which ligand-to-iron ratio is one or two. The ligand generates much interest for its diverse coordination modes⁵, such as bidentate, tridentate, meridional or bridging. Six- and seven-coordinate iron complexes with mononuclear, binuclear and polynuclear structures are also reported^{1,2}.

The ligand is useful in decontamination of nuclear reactors⁶, in corrosion inhibition⁶ and has diverse biological activities⁷. Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid enhances the production of spore photoproducts in bacterial spores upon UV-irradiation and as its calcium salts is thought to be responsible for the heat resistant property⁸ of its spores. Iron complexes of the ligand have been utilized as electron carriers in some model biological system⁹ and as specific molecular tools in DNA cleavage⁹.

We report here the preparation and crystal structure of Ph₄As[Fe^{III}L₂] (Ph = phenyl).

Results and Discussion

Single crystal X-ray data of the title complex are given in Table 1, together with refinement details. X-ray diffrac-

tion study revealed the structure (Fig. 1) as distorted octahedral, Fe sitting at the centre and surrounded by two ONO-tridentate ligands. Table 2 contains a list of selected bond distances and angles. The unit cell contains four Ph₄As[FeL₂] units.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for Ph₄As[Fe^{III}L₂]

Empirical formula	C ₃₆ H ₂₆ AsFeN ₂ O ₈
Formula weight	769.38
Temp.	293(3) K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	C ₂ /c
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 25.157(3)$ Å $b = 10.1980(7)$ Å $c = 27.504(3)$ Å
	$\alpha = 90^\circ$ $\beta = 107.191(7)^\circ$ $\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume, Z	6741.0(12) Å ³ , 4
Density (calcd.)	1.516 mg/m ³
Absorption coefficient	1.479 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	3128
Crystal size	0.42 × 0.85 × 0.72 mm
θ range for data collection	2.39–27.50°
Limiting indices	0 ≤ h ≤ 32, -13 ≤ k ≤ 0, -35 ≤ l ≤ 34
Reflections collected	7772
Independent reflections	7601 (R _{int} = 0.0219)
Completeness to θ = 27.50°	98.2%
Max. and min. transmission	0.8279 and 0.4699
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F ²
Data/restraints/parameters	7601/0/478
Goodness of fit on F ²	1.046
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)]	R1 = 0.0405, wR2 = 0.0890
R indices (all data)	R1 = 0.0674, wR2 = 0.1022
Extinction coefficient	0.00198(9)
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.395 and -0.81 eÅ
Ph = Phenyl	

Fig. 1. Displacement ellipsoid drawing (20% probability) of the [Fe^{III}L₂]⁺ cation, showing the atom-numbering scheme.

The present complex is monoclinic like Na[FeL₂]. 2H₂O³; (H₃O)₂[FeL₂]⁴ is orthorhombic. The striking difference of the title complex with the above two complexes is the complete absence of water molecules, coordinated or

hydrated. As a result, the extensive H-bonding involving the water molecules is absent. All the hydrogens of the phenyl groups are involved in intramolecular H-bonding with oxygen atoms of the carboxyl groups. The bond distances range from 2.968 to 1.693 Å. The hydrogens of pyridine rings are involved in both intramolecular and intermolecular H-bonding with the O-atoms of carboxyl groups. The average intramolecular bond distance is 2.80 Å while the intermolecular H-bonding range from 2.960 to 1.960 Å. The pyridine nitrogen of the ligand also participates in the H-bonding (C23-H23-N1A : 1.693 Å and C23-H23-N1B : 1.693 Å).

Table 2. Selected bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) of $\text{Ph}_4\text{As}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}_2]$

Bond length (Å)			
Fe-O(11A)	2.001(2)	Fe-O(71A)	2.010(2)
Fe-O(71B)	2.020(2)	Fe-O(11B)	2.027(2)
Fe-N(1A)	2.053(2)	Fe-N(1B)	2.067(2)
O(11A)-C(1A)	1.294(4)	O(12A)-C(1A)	1.215(4)
O(71A)-C(7A)	1.291(4)	O(72A)-C(7A)	1.219(4)
N(1A)-C(2A)	1.327(4)	N(1A)-C(6A)	1.327(3)
Angle (°)			
O(11A)-Fe-O(71A)	151.35(9)	O(11A)-Fe-O(71B)	91.92(10)
O(71A)-Fe-O(71B)	93.58(10)	O(11A)-Fe-O(11B)	96.46(10)
O(71A)-Fe-O(11B)	92.11(9)	O(71B)-Fe-O(11B)	151.21(9)
O(11A)-Fe-N(1A)	75.88(9)	O(71A)-Fe-N(1A)	76.00(9)
O(71B)-Fe-N(1A)	112.19(9)	O(11B)-Fe-N(1A)	96.57(9)
O(11A)-Fe-N(1B)	104.30(9)	O(71A)-Fe-N(1B)	104.31(9)
O(71B)-Fe-N(1B)	75.71(8)	O(11B)-Fe-N(1B)	75.54(9)
N(1A)-Fe-N(1B)	172.10(9)	C(1A)-O(11A)-Fe	120.98(19)
C(1B)-O(11B)-Fe	120.95(18)	C(7A)-O(71A)-Fe	120.37(19)
C(7B)-O(71B)-Fe	120.90(19)	C(6A)-N(1A)-Fe	118.50(19)
C(2A)-N(1A)-Fe	118.80(19)	C(2B)-N(1B)-Fe	118.85(19)

Ph = Phenyl

The two ligands in the complex anion are meridional; the pyridine rings retain their approximate C_{2v} symmetry. The Fe-O (2.001(2)-2.027(2) Å) and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$ bonds (2.053(2)-2.067(2) Å) are equivalent to $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-O}$ and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$ bonds in other $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}$ complexes. However, they are shorter than their counterparts in $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{-L}$ complexes. This is expected due to higher charge and hence smaller ionic radius. No comparison is, however, drawn between $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$ and $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{-N}$ bond distances here, since their bonds are found to cover¹⁰ a very wide range (1.90-2.75 Å). $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-O}$ and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$ bond distances of various $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}$ complexes are given in Table 3.

Table 3. $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-O}$ and $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$ bond distances of different $\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-L}$ complexes

Compd.*	Bond distance (Å)		Ref.
	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-O}$	$\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{-N}$	
$\text{Na}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.000(3)-2.053(3)	2.057(3)	2
$[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}(\text{Cl})(\text{OH}_2)_2]$	2.032(2)-2.046(2)	2.066(3)	1
$\text{Ph}_4\text{As}[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}_2]$	2.001(2)-2.027(2)	2.053(2)-2.067(2)	This work
$[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}(\text{OH}_2)_3][\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{L}_2] \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.008(2)-2.028(2)	2.054(2)-2.059(2)	3

*Ph = Phenyl, H_2L = pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid.

Experimental

Pyridine-2,6-dicarboxylic acid (Schuchardt) was used as obtained. $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck) and tetraphenylarsonium chloride (Merck) were of A.R. grade. The complex was prepared by reacting aqueous solutions of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2L in 1 : 2 molar ratio, and stirring for 0.5 h at $\sim 90^\circ$. To the resulting green solution, excess of solid tetraphenylarsonium chloride was added. Shiny light-green crystalline product separated instantaneously. Single crystals were obtained from DMSO/water mixture.

X-ray crystallography : Crystals of the complex were glued to the ends of a thin glass fiber and transferred to a Siemens P4/S diffractometer using $\text{MoK}(\alpha)$ and graphite monochromator. Cell dimensions and an orientation matrix for data collection were obtained from a least-squares refinement of the setting angles of at least 25 accurately centered reflections. The structures were solved by direct methods using the SHELXTL package of computer programs¹¹. Neutral atom scattering factors were used¹² with corrections for real and imaginary anomalous dispersion¹³. All structures were refined by full-matrix least-square methods based on F^2 using SHELXTL-96¹⁴ and used all unique data. Non-hydrogen atoms were located in difference Fourier syntheses and refined isotropically. Additional material available from the authors comprises of hydrogen atom coordinates, complete set of bond distances and angles, atomic coordinates and anisotropic displacement parameters.

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